

Research Paper

Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences among LIC in Teaching Professionals with Special Reference to MBA Colleges in Tumkur - A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This is a descriptive study based on the investors' behaviour and investment preferences of teaching professionals. The main purpose of this study is to know the investment preferences of investors when choosing LIC policies over other investment avenues. For this study, the respondents are teaching professionals. What are the different factors that may affect their investment decisions and their diversification strategies? This may include the financial goals, awareness of different financial products, and earlier investment experiences of the respondents. This research may determine the level of awareness of LIC products, their benefits, and their features.

Research Design/ Methodology: The study was conducted based on primary sources of information. Primary data are collected from 65 teaching professions at MBA colleges in Tumkur city. Seven colleges were taken into consideration for the study, which adopted a convenient sampling technique.

Findings/ Result: The study consisted of middle-aged people, and their educational level and experiences played a significant role in their investment knowledge and decisions. Based on the mean value of 3.11 on influencing factors, it was found that the respondent's preferences and factors are varied. After analyzing the average scores for the Strengths of Investing in LIC and Weaknesses of LIC criteria, they were 2.45 and 2.62, respectively. This implies that respondents saw LIC as an investment choice with both pros and cons. According to the mean value of 2.89 for Other Investment Awareness, respondents have a minimum awareness level of other investing possibilities than LIC.

Originality/Value: This analysis stands out because of the way it particularly analyzes LIC policies within the behavioral finance paradigm. The findings may help in a greater understanding of demographic factors like age, gender, education level, and teaching experience. Investment and financial choices may be influenced by these variables. Additionally, LIC and other players in the financial services industry receive useful information from the examination of characteristics linked to LIC products, such as strengths, weaknesses, and influencing factors. The findings will enable investors to modify investment strategies and products to suit the needs and tastes of diverse demographic groups. Additionally, they offer a framework for guidelines and standards for future behavioural finance research. The study also emphasizes the importance of investor's skills and knowledge in influencing financial decisions, especially in the area of investing in life insurance.

Paper Type: Case Study

Key Words: Investors' Behaviour, Investment Preferences, Teaching Professionals, LIC, Investment Decision.

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I. INTRODUCTION:

Understanding investors' behaviour and their distinctive investing choices has emerged as a crucial field of research in the dynamic world of global finance. Investor psychology and a financial perspective on investments are combined to understand and explain investors' behaviour. This method is used to examine the psychological actions taken by investors during the planning and decision-making stages of their investment activities. In addition, company performance and economic fundamentals, human psychology, emotions, and

decision-making play a complex role in the financial markets. The behaviour of investors increasingly influences market movements, asset prices, and the stability of the financial system as a whole. (1)

Investment is an economic outlook, and it is one of the financial assets in the financial market that are not consumed today but will provide income or returns in the future. Investment is depositing the money that has been saved from present expenses in anticipation of future rewards. To get the rewards, people need to invest, which is called as savings. An investment is a sacrifice of current funds and other resources for future advantages. In the present scenario, there are various savings schemes and investment options available, like Insurance, Post Office Schemes, Fixed Deposits, Shares, Bonds, Mutual Funds, and So on. An in-depth knowledge of investment concepts and their options helps investors build a portfolio on their investments by maximizing their returns while reducing their risk. (2)

In the investment procedure, present expenditure is sacrificed to make good earnings in the future. Investor's investments may be known, but their appreciation for their investments is unknown. Investors expend their money in the form of savings, but it is income for the future and not expendable. Various behavioural factors influence investor's savings; some of them are gender, income level, qualification, occupation, and so on. Every investor is a saver, but not all savers are investors. Investments are made with the intention of generating a suitable return throughout the holding period by converting financial wealth into physical wealth. The two elements of an investment decision are risk and reward, and some of the factors that affect every investment decision are: investment alternatives, aim of investment, duration of investment, and proper trading of alternatives. (3)

Investors always prefer to invest for more rewards with minimal risk. Among various investment alternatives, investing in LIC policies has provided risk-free returns and protection against their investments. The Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) is one of the biggest and entrusted institutions, providing various insurance products and investment options. Teaching professionals have a stable income level and tend to look for financial security for their investments. Many professionals have chosen LIC plans for their investment options in order to safeguard their financial prospects. To sustain their families, these regulations take into consideration future needs and requirements.

II. RELATED WORKS:

2.1 Investors' Behaviour:

Understanding investors' behaviour is crucial for financial analysts, fund managers, and policymakers as it helps explain market changes. The term "investors' behaviour" refers to a variety of psychological and emotional aspects that affect how each individual investor manages their investments and participates in the financial market. Financial advisors face a difficult time coming up with marketing tactics since investors are well aware of the value of financial investments, and they also have trouble understanding the investors' behaviour and investment preferences. (4)

The main outcomes of a systematic literature review utilizing the keywords "Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences" in the Google Scholar databases are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Review of Investor's Behaviour and Investment Preferences

Sl No	Field of Research	Focus	Contribution	References
1.	Financial Literacy and Investment Behaviour	IT professionals' level of satisfaction with financial services provided by investment firms.	Majority of investors prefer medium term investment with medium risk and return.	Mahabub Basha S, et.al
2	Financial literacy, Savings and Investment behaviour of IT Professionals	Examine the likelihood of saving, the manner in which investors behave, and the level of financial understanding among IT professionals.	The relationship among people's savings and investment decision and their financial literacy.	Seema Gupta, June 2023
3	Saving and Investment Behaviour of IT Professionals	The study is to understand Bangalore's IT professional's savings and investment habits. IT professionals have caught the interest of economists, but their earnings are unrealized.	It gives a road map for economic planners, financial institutions, organizational managers, and investors to develop the best plan for boosting investment opportunities as well as strengthening India and its growth.	Anju K J, et.al, June 2017
4	Investment Behaviour of Individual Investor's	Understanding individual investors' behaviour across a range of investment opportunities	Investors should be conscious of their investment decisions. Although every person has different requirements for their goals, everyone's ultimate objective is to maximize profits. Therefore, financial institutions should train investors in effective savings management.	Dr. Deepak Kumar Agarwal, et.al, September 2021

5	Investment Behaviour with respect to Financial Knowledge and Preference of Investment Risk	Know the relationship between investor knowledge and their investment behaviour through different channels.	Since different sorts of investors take different types of risks based on their investment behaviour, there is no connection between investment behaviour and knowledge level.	Smita Mazumdar
6	Investment Preference and Behaviour of Individual Investors	Investigate individuals Investment choices and their behaviour toward investing in different alternatives.	Most investors often invest in financial assets like deposits, gold, and silver; however, before making an investment, investors should learn about their options and get familiar with their options through educational programs.	K. Parimalakanthi, et.al, December 2015
7	Saving Habit and Investment Preference of Government School Teachers	Discover the respondent's investment preferences and the numerous factors influencing their saving decisions in order to ascertain their saving habits.	As their standard of living increased, teachers came to understand the value of investing in various possibilities for future requirements. They began their investments for the future in order to benefit from future needs, which may include their children's schooling, marriage, and other things.	V. Dhayalan, et.al, April, 2019
8	Comparative Study of Investment Preferences in Public Sector and Private Sector Enterprises	The investigation's focus is on identifying the differences in investment preferences between public sector enterprises (PSEs) and private sector enterprises (PRISEs). The study attempts to shed insight on the variables driving these two unique business sectors' diverse investment strategies as well as the city's overall economic environment.	The study uses thorough survey methodology and data analysis to provide insightful information about how PSEs and PRISEs manage their financial resources, with significant implications for decision-makers, investors, and companies. The sustainable growth and development of Mangalore City may be facilitated by improved financial planning and resource allocation, which may be facilitated by an understanding of the investment patterns in various sectors.	Dr. Dharmananda M. et al, 2023
9	Investors Behaviour towards the investment alternatives	Examine the relative importance of different socioeconomic factors in investment decisions and explore the sources of investor motivation.	Most of the investor's primary concern for their investment is safety, and having long-term investment experience with medium-term base and tax savings is a key concern for their investment. The investors recommended that, in order to clarify the investments, financial institutions develop investment strategies that would yield the maximum returns in the shortest length of time.	Satveer Kaur, et.al, March 2018
10	Factors Affecting Customer Investment Towards Life Insurance Policies	Examination of, how various demographic characteristics affect investors choices about their purchase of life insurance and consider investors preferences while making an investment decision in LIC.	Everybody should get life insurance since it is a crucial type of protection. Compared to wealthy countries where practically all lives are covered and the stage of saturation has been reached, India has very little usage of life insurance. There are numerous elements that influence investors decisions to invest in life insurance, but the study's findings show that demographic factors in the population have a significant and crucial bearing on whether or not they choose to buy life insurance policies.	Ms. Babita Yadav, et.al, July 2012
11	Factors influencing Customer Preference towards Investment in Life Insurance Policies	Explore the various insurance options available today and the association between demographic characteristics and insurance preferences.	Investors are the true foundation for the growth of the various insurance policies, and demographic variables also play a significant role in the development of the market for LIC products.	Nivedha V, et.al, 2023
12	Investors Preference towards Life Insurance Corporation of India	The investors' attitudes about life insurance and the focus were only on public sector life insurance and policyholders' preferences.	Successful investing decisions involve knowledge and competence. If the investor carefully analyzes the published facts, skill is required to assess the risk and return associated with an investment with minimal risk.	B. Sumathisri, July 2017
13	Investment Behaviour of Businessmen	Create a profile of a typical Indian individual investor that includes information on their demographics and learn about the businessmen's preferred investment horizons.	Most businessmen are unaware of contemporary financial goods and have no concept how much money can be made from them. The research focused on businessmen's investing behaviour, which suggests that they may lack capital or lack motivation in making investments.	Dr. Vinod K. Bhatnagar, 2011

14	Investment Behaviour of Households	Concentrate on the various income sources and levels of the various household categories, as well as the attitudes of the families toward the various investments they can make, and determine how well-informed investors are about the various tax-saving measures.	The majority of household investors are content with their income and have extra money each month, so they look for new investment opportunities, which will boost the nation's economy as well.	Shwetam Gupta, et.al, 2023
15	Life Insurance Policies as an Investment options for Investors	Investors' opinions of life insurance as a possible investment, their level of knowledge about various life insurance products, and their satisfaction level while investing in its products	Insurance protects against unforeseen events that could happen in the future. This is mostly due to the fact that investors demand financial security and safety when they invest in life insurance products.	Kavya T A, et.al, April 2023
16	Investment Decisions and Challenges Of Working Women Policyholder towards Life Insurance Corporation	Discover the socioeconomic characteristics of female policyholders in collaboration with the Life Insurance Corporation and how a woman with life insurance makes investment decisions.	Women today invest to secure their own futures or the futures of their children, which leads to an active role in the family's financial decision-making and shows how crucial it is for life insurance product marketers and advertising to effectively include and engage women in their communication. However, women, particularly those who experience catastrophic incidents, must receive specific attention for their survival.	Ms. S.Pradeepa,et.al, September 2022

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The study comprehensively observes investors' behaviour and investment preferences for various investment alternatives specifically related to LIC products among teaching professionals and what other factors can affect their financial decisions. This may include:

1. To study the factors affecting the investment choices of teaching professionals.
2. To Study the investment preferences of investors when choosing LIC policies than other investment options.
- 3 To evaluate the time horizon of teaching professionals when investing in LIC.
- 4 To study about financial knowledge and awareness among teaching professionals regarding LIC policies.
5. To conduct SWOT analysis on investment preference to the investors on LIC policies and its benefits.

IV. METHODOLOGY:

The information is obtained from primary and secondary sources. A well-structured questionnaire is used to collect data on demographics and investment-related characteristics among teaching professionals. 65 participants were selected as the sample size for this study using convenience sampling methods. The data were computed using SPSS software, and the appropriate statistical tools, such as tables, percentages, means, and standard deviation tools, were used to evaluate and interpret the data acquired. Various kinds of websites, academic journals, and publications are used to collect secondary data for the study.

V. FINANCIAL MARKET:

Financial markets are locations for the buying and selling of a variety of financial items, including stocks, bonds, commodities, currencies, and derivatives. These markets act as an essential mechanism for the movement of capital throughout the economy. Financial markets are used by traders and investors to buy goods they forecast to increase in value over time or to control risks related to their investments. Financial markets can be virtual trading platforms or physical places like stock exchanges.

Many different functions are performed by financial markets.

- **Allocation of Capital:** They make it possible for organizations, institutions, and individual investors to raise money by creating and exchanging financial instruments. Companies can raise funds, for instance, by issuing shares on the stock market.
- **Price Discovery:** Financial markets assist in determining asset prices based on supply and demand patterns as well as a number of external sources, such as economic data and news events.
- **Liquidity:** Markets allow investors to easily buy or sell assets, increasing liquidity and lowering the likelihood of significant price movements.
- **Risk Management:** Investors can use the financial markets to manage or hedge the risks related to their assets. Investors can safeguard themselves against unexpected price movements, for instance, using derivatives like options and futures.

5.1 Financial Advisors:

An expert who offers guidance and advice on several aspects of investing and personal finance is known as a financial advisor. The decision-making process for managing funds, achieving financial goals, and navigating the complexity of the financial markets is assisted by financial advisors for both individuals and organizations.

Financial advisors can be of various types.

- **Financial planners:** These experts assist individuals in developing detailed financial plans by taking into consideration factors including spending, saving, investing, retirement planning, and estate planning. They develop individualized plans to assist individuals in achieving their financial goals.
- **Investment Advisors:** Advisors that focus on helping individuals make investment decisions are known as investment advisors. To suggest appropriate investment strategies and asset allocations, they consider an investor's risk tolerance, financial objectives, and time horizon.
- **Wealth Managers:** Wealth managers offer comprehensive financial services to high-net-worth individuals and families, such as investment management, tax preparation, estate planning, and risk management.
- **Financial Consultants:** These experts help individuals buy and sell securities in the financial markets. They might offer market analysis and advice on specific investments.

5.2 Investment

Investment is the method of investing money or capital into various businesses or assets in the expectation of making money in the future. Creating wealth and attaining financial goals like Children's education, marriage, retirement planning, constructing a house, and creating a safety net for future benefits are the main purposes of investing in different types of alternatives. Investments commonly include the purchase of physical or financial assets with the goal of generating income or capital growth for the investor. Investment can be understood as the giving up of some present value in exchange for a reward for the future. There are some investments that only produce income, such as bank deposits, post office certificates, company deposits, life insurance, mutual funds, chit funds, and real estate. Some of the Investments are recorded as capital gains if they are made in the form of assets like stock in a firm, real estate, or other comparable assets. Investing in government securities that are listed on a reputable stock exchange, however, is simple to transfer and market. Risky investments are those whose values change greatly and whose rewards are unknown.

5.3 Different Investment Alternatives

Any investment has as its main goal the long-term maximization of the investor's financial welfare. Maximizing an investor's wealth and making use of the liquidity that wealth provides are two critical components of investor welfare. The phrase "wealth maximization" is further broken down into three parts: cash return, capital growth, and safety. As a result, the goals of investors can be summed up as follows:

Appreciation of Capital

One of the main goals of investing is the appreciation of capital. Real or financial assets are used in investments. Real assets are material possessions like real estate, buildings, cars, and bullion, whereas financial assets are things like stock certificates that have an indirect claim to actual assets held by others.

Security

Investors prioritize security as their primary goal when making investments with their hard-earned cash. Many investors are very dissatisfied with the low yield of investments because security is an important factor.

Liquidity

Investors typically favor investments that offer greater liquidity. Bank savings accounts and term deposits are typically easily redeemable. Only when the frequency, timing, and severity of the investors' liquidity needs cannot be predicted in advance can liquidity have any real value.

Tax Benefits

The interest the investor receives from his investment is taxable income, and in some circumstances, tax must be withheld from interest income at source (TDS). Some Tax laws help reduce tax liability.

Real Estate

Real Estate investment is becoming more popular today. It may include land, buildings, and house property, and on a long-term basis, the value increases faster than the deposits.

Life Insurance

A life insurance contract provides for payments of a certain amount to the insured party from the insurance provider upon the occurrence of the event covered. The main goal of purchasing a life insurance policy is to cover risk, but the policy has recently started to resemble an investment.

Mutual Fund

A trust that invests money in stocks, bonds, money market instruments, and/or other securities after collecting funds from a number of participants who have similar investing goals. The categories of mutual funds are set up so that investors can select a plan based on the level of risk they are ready to accept, the amount they can invest, their objectives, the length of the investment, etc.

Government Bonds

These are also known as Gilt-Edged bonds and are issued by state and central governments. These securities usually have a lower rate of interest, high safety and liquidity, and an income and capital claim on the government. These have a very large market in India. The two most important types of government securities are stock certificates and promissory notes.

5.4 Investment Decision based on Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences.

Investors' behaviour, preferences, and financial objectives play a crucial role in the investment decision-making process. Various psychological, financial, and individual factors have an impact on these decisions. Investors invest for a variety of reasons. Few of the investors invest to get benefits for their retirement, and others may invest to increase their wealth or their returns. Other types of investors make investments in order to expand their savings or get tax advantages. Every type of investment choice may have its own risks; it depends on the type of investment and how the investor chooses his investment choices.

The following are the common risks associated with investing:

- **Political Risk:** This type of risk is that a political development will have an unfavorable effect on the investments and their value.
- **Market Risk:** In this type of risk, the value of an investment may decline based on market situations.
- **Liquidity Risk:** Investors are unable to sell their securities quickly due to liquidity risk.
- **Interest Rate Uncertainties:** In this category, the value of the investment decreases when the interest rate rises.

5.4.1 Investors' Behaviour

Investors' behaviour is defined as the actions, judgments, and responses that people or groups of people exhibit when selecting an investment and the manner in which investors make their investment decisions.

Investors' behaviour influences numerous factors, some of which are:

- **Risk Tolerance:** Again, this will be influenced by the investor's age, gender, education, income level, and financial objectives. In these, some of the investors prefer safe investments and are risk-averse, while others are risk-tolerant and pursue bigger returns even at the expense of greater risk.
- **Market Situation:** Investors' behaviour can change based on market volatility, geopolitical developments. Bull markets and Bear markets give directions for the movement of securities in the market. Bull markets might stimulate more risk-taking, while bear markets might make people more cautious.
- **Psychological Biases:** Investment decisions can be influenced by psychological biases such as loss aversion, confirmation bias, and herding behaviour. Investors make decisions or take action irrationally based more on emotion than rationale.
- **Availability of Information:** Investors' perceptions and actions regarding the availability of data in the market are influenced by how easily information can be acquired by using social media platforms. To make quick decisions, real-time data is necessary.

5.4.2 Investment Preference

Investment preferences refer to the specific choices that investors prefer to make when investing in numerous assets and industries and applying various investment strategies. The risk tolerance, investing objectives, time horizon, and financial status of the investor are different variables that have an impact on these preferences.

5.4.3 Some of the factors that can influence investment preferences are:

Risk Tolerance: An investor is willing to assume this level of risk. Bonds or other less risky investments may be preferred by investors with a low risk tolerance compared to those with a high-risk tolerance, who are more likely to invest in equities.

Investment objectives: This is the justification behind an investor's investment. Cash equivalents or other safe assets may be preferred by investors with short-term objectives, such as saving for a down payment on a home. Long-term investors, such as those saving for retirement, can be more inclined to invest in stocks or other risky investments.

Time Horizon: Short-term investors might favor financial instruments or other secure assets, whereas long-term investors might be more ready to invest in stocks or other riskier assets.

Financial Status: Investors income level, assets, and liabilities are all included in this financial scenario. Investors who are in a good financial position might be more inclined to take risks than investors who are in weaker sections, and vice versa, when it comes to risk.

VI. LIC INSURANCE INDUSTRY:

Selecting the best investment scheme will be complicated for every type of investor. In every individual's life, risks might be assured or unpredictable. One of the oldest and biggest Insurance company in India for individual lives is the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC). This institution is owned by the state, offering a variety of investment plans and insurance coverage possibilities for the general public. Throughout the Insurance sector in India, LIC plays a major role in promoting awareness of life insurance and its benefits.

There are a wide variety of networks and agencies that LIC maintains in India. Every individual can easily contact LIC branches or agencies anywhere in India. This insurance industry has substantially contributed to the economic growth of the country by exploiting individual savings or investments and offering long-term financial benefits for their developmental and infrastructural projects.

Based on LIC's ownership by the government and the wealth of the insurance sector's experiences, LIC policies are very popular for their predictability and transparency. LIC has expanded the variety of products and services it offers to its investors in order to meet demand, needs and expectations.

6.1 LIC provides several different types of insurance coverage, including

1. **Term insurance:** Offers protection for a predetermined term or length of time. The beneficiary receives the death benefit if the policyholder passes away during the term.
2. **Whole life insurance:** Provides protection for the insured for the whole of their life. When the policyholder passes away, it gives the recipient a death benefit.
3. **Endowment Plans:** These types of plans combine savings with insurance. If the bearer of the policy lives to the end of the policy term, it offers both a death benefit and a maturity benefit.
4. **Money-Back Policies:** These contracts offer recurrent payments over the course of the policy term, which might assist policyholders in covering frequent expenses.
5. **Unit-Linked Insurance Plans (ULIPs):** These are investment-insurance plans that also offer insurance protection and permit policyholders to invest in a range of funds.
6. **Pension Plans:** Also referred to as retirement savings plans, these insurance policies guarantee the policyholder a steady income after their retirement.
7. **Health Insurance:** In addition, LIC provides medical expense and hospitalization insurance plans.
8. **Child Plans:** These plans are made to cover a child's future expenses, including those related to their education and marriage.

6.2 Knowledge and Awareness of LIC Products among Investors

In India, people are familiar with LIC products, and the industry has significantly contributed to raising knowledge of life insurance and financial planning in the nation. However, investor knowledge and awareness of LIC products can vary depending on factors like education, socioeconomic level, and experience with financial education programs.

The below data represents the investor's knowledge and awareness of LIC and its products.

Traditional Products: The investors are familiar with LIC's old products, like Endowment Plans, whole Life Insurance Policies, and Money-Back Insurance Policies. These products have existed for many years, and now people frequently refer to life insurance.

Term insurance: This insurance is raising its value by providing pure life insurance benefits to its investors. In order to protect their family's financial future, many investors are aware of the importance of having a fundamental life insurance policy.

Unit-Linked Insurance Plans (ULIPs): This is also one of the financial products that combine investment and insurance. Although people are becoming more aware of these products, some investors may find it difficult to understand the investment component and fees related to ULIPs.

Pension Plans: Although awareness of retirement savings and pension schemes is rising, it may not yet be at the same level as that of other insurance products.

VII. SWOT ANALYSIS:

SWOT stands for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and Threats. This helps to know about the LIC products and their benefits. Some of the concepts on investors' perceptions of the LIC Products are listed below:

7.1 Strength

The LIC brand has a solid reputation and a long history in India. Due to their propensity for long-term thinking, teaching professionals frequently focus on long-term insurance and investment options in LIC products.

Additionally, thanks to Sections 80C and 10(10D) of the Income Tax Act, LIC products offer tax benefits to the numerous teaching professionals who may be attracted to these tax-saving options. However, the extensive LIC agent network provides in-person consultations, which may appeal to teaching professionals who appreciate personalized support.

7.2 Weakness

Teaching professionals might not be as knowledgeable about all LIC products offered outside of popular plans, which might make them less likely to seek alternative solutions. Some LIC products, particularly those tied to investments, can be complex. It could be challenging for teaching professionals to understand the specifics of these products without adequate knowledge of finance.

7.3 Opportunities

In order to educate professionals about LIC products and their benefits, LIC can organize conferences, seminars, workshops, and training sessions. Plans designed for teachers, such as those that offer them extra freedom over the summer, could be profitable in this industry. By using digital platforms to provide tutorials and clear information about LIC products, it would be possible to eliminate the knowledge gap.

7.4 Threats

Teaching professionals have a variety of investment options open to them, including Mutual Funds, Shares, Post Office Schemes, and other Financial Products that could divert their focus. Changes to tax regulations or laws governing investments and insurance may have an effect on how appealing LIC products are. Due to their regular busy schedules, teaching professionals rarely have enough time for in-depth study or financial product decision-making.

ANALYSIS:

Table No: 2 Percentage Analysis – Demographic Profile

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	35	53.8
	Female	30	46.2
	Total	65	100.0
Age	25 – 35 Years	17	26.2
	36 – 45 Years	36	55.4
	46 – 55 Years	11	16.9
	56 and above	1	1.5
	Total	65	100.0
Qualification	Masters Degree	48	73.8
	Doctorate	17	26.2
	Total	65	100.0
Teaching Experience	Less Than 5 Years	14	21.5
	5 – 10 Years	19	29.2
	10 - 15 Years	22	33.8
	15 Years and above	10	15.4
	Total	65	100.0
Income Per Anum	0 – 5 Lakh	21	32.3
	5 – 10 Lakh	25	38.5
	10 – 15 Lakh	11	16.9
	15 and above	8	12.3
	Total	65	100.0

Table 2 indicates the demographic profile of the respondents. As per the table, 53.8% are male and 46.2 are female respondents. It indicates that the sample's gender distribution is approximately equal. 55.4% of respondent's age group is 36.45 years, and the data shows that the majority of respondents have completed their master's degree with 10 to 15 years of teaching experience, and their income level lies between 5 lakh and 10 lakh. It was useful for learning about the characteristics of the individuals who participated in the study.

Table 3: Calculation of Descriptive Statistics for Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences in LIC among Teaching Professionals.

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Investment Choices Factors	2.63	1.464
Goal of Making Financial Decision	2.34	.871

Knowledge and Awareness on LIC	2.25	.830
Influencing Factor of selecting LIC	3.11	1.542
Investment Product in LIC	2.89	1.371
Duration of Investment	2.43	.968
Proportion of Investment in LIC	2.00	.984
LIC as an Investment Opportunity	2.77	1.332
Reasons for Choosing LIC Policies	2.69	1.457
Satisfaction of LIC Policies than other options	2.22	.857
Assessment and Revaluation of LIC Policies	2.29	.931
Suggestions of LIC Policies to Others	2.29	.897
Strength of Investing in LIC	2.45	1.225
Weakness of LIC	2.62	1.331
Investment Strategies	2.02	.673
Other Investment Awareness	2.89	1.552

The variation of the factors on Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences is analyzed with mean and standard deviation, and the output is presented in Table 3. It is noted that many factors influence the selection of LIC policies among teaching professionals. The mean rating for the factor that influences choosing LIC is 3.11, and the standard deviation is a relatively high 1.542, demonstrating that a variety of factors influence LIC selection. When we discuss the mean investment in the LIC rating of 2.00, This mean score indicates that, on average, respondents only invested a small portion of their money into LIC. However, as the standard deviation of 0.984 indicates, there is some variation or dispersion in the responses. Even though the mean allocation is 2.00, the preferences of individual respondents may differ greatly from this average. The observed standard deviation may be the result of different responders allocating different amounts of money to LIC. Given this situation, research shows that respondents' investment allocation choices for LIC vary, with some being more conservative and others more adventurous.

VIII. ABCD ANALYSIS:

Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences can be analyzed using ABCD analysis in this section. The qualitative analysis has been made using ABCD, where the Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages are connected to this framework.

8.1 Advantages

- 1) It provides an understanding of Investors' Behaviour and Investment Preferences among LIC products.
- 2) It clearly understands what types of factors can influence the investors decision-making process.
- 3) It gives detailed experiences about investors financial goals, risk tolerance level, and standard of living behaviour.
- 4) It finds out the improvement areas in product developmental activities, creates awareness among investors about LIC products, and monitors their preferences to invest in LIC and its product.

8.2 Benefits

- 1) To understand the investor decision-making process, the institutions can enhance the development of educational programs and provide financial knowledge to the investors to make a proper decision at the time of their investments.
- 2) It helps to develop more short-term and long-term investment products for their investors.
- 3) It builds strong relationships between the financial institution and their investors, so it increases brand loyalty among their policyholders.
- 4) It enhances investors' perceptions of the institution and may reduce the risk at the time of investment.

8.3 Constraints

- 1) It may be difficult to gather investment-related information from various types of investors and to protect this information highly confidentially.

- 2) Due to the small sample size, it is difficult to generalize the findings of the study.
- 3) It required a lot of time and experts for collecting data, data editing, coding, and analysis purposes.

8.4 Disadvantages

- 1) A Large amount of data can be difficult to manage for analysis.
- 2) Qualitative data takes more time to analyze when compared to quantitative data.
- 3) If strict methodology is not followed in qualitative data, the Investors' Behaviour may be misinterpreted.
- 4) Qualitative data analysis may have the risk of generalizing Investors' Behaviour in financial decision making.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS:

According to the study, the majority of the respondents have a master's degree. Financial awareness and knowledge may vary among each other. By offering financial education and workshops that are specific to their needs, we can improve their investment decision-making based on their level of understanding and income level. For different investment-related parameters, the mean values and standard deviations show variations in preferences and disparities. For instance, use this knowledge to improve overall satisfaction by learning why some respondents are happier with LIC plans than other alternatives. Recognize teachers' various investment strategies and offer them various LIC products and investing instruments to match their various risk appetites and objectives. In relation to LIC, acknowledge the respondents' perceptions of its deficiencies. Transparency, customer service, and product adaptability should all be improved to relieve such concerns. To effectively advertise LIC plans, make use of the respondents' perceived strengths. Maintain regular campaigns, seminars, and workshops to spread awareness and information on LIC products.

X. CONCLUSIONS:

According to the survey, there are a variety of differences among teaching professionals in terms of their age, education, teaching experience, and income levels. The majority of the respondents are in the middle of their careers; this may have a different impact on their investing decisions than it would on younger or older people. **When it comes to financial planning and investing decisions, teaching experience can be important, with experienced professionals possibly having different objectives. Teachers are usually familiar with different financial terms and concepts, which may help them manage their personal finances. Teachers know the importance of savings for retirement, and as a result, they usually opt for long-term financial planning to get huge benefits at their retirement stage. Hence, they believe that LIC and its products may fulfill their satisfaction in their retirement lives.** Further analysis and investigation may be required to better understand their investment behaviour and preferences, including an investigation into specific aspects that affect their investment decisions and how these factors relate to their demographic characteristics.

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